

INTERNET ACCESS AND USAGE: IMPACT ON STUDENTS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN SOCIAL STUDIES

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Abstract:

The study investigated the impact of Internet access and usage on students' academic performance in Social Studies. The study adopted a correlational research design. The population consisted of 55,303 male and female JSS II students from which 576 students were selected. The instrument for the study was the questionnaire and students' academic records. The data collected were analysed using correlational statistics. The result of the study revealed that there is significant relationship between internet usage for academic work and students' academic performance; there is significant relationship between internet access and usage and students' assignment submission; there was significant relationship between time spent on the internet and students' academic performance. It was recommended that students should use the internet to enhance their academic performance of which they should restrict themselves from non-academic purposes; teachers should evolve regulations to guide the extent of Internet usage to avert over dependency among students.

Keywords: internet; internet access; internet usage; impact, academic performance; secondary school; social studies

1. Introduction

The internet and its usage is of very great importance in our day to day living for being a source of channel for information enlightenments, information gathering, access to important and relevant academic materials for the teaching and learning likewise for socialization and fun. It has brought hope for students in particular and young generations in general There has been a never before seen growth in the numbers of

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internet users since the 1990s According to Computer Almanac (2003) over 160 million people accessed the internet in United States of America (USA), over 120 million people in Europe and more than 60 million people in Africa. The numbers of those who access the internet keep on increasing.

Conversely, so as to meet the demand of educational tasks, educational (schools) institutions in the country are asking for more internet aided instruction (IAI) and initialization of different technology with education. The internet had long been use in the society and educational system. Teachers, students and the society at large have been feeling greatly the usefulness and the effect of the internet. Also, according to Anderson (2009), the internet can be problematic or filled with problems to the users, especially with the youths. Such problems may be in form of those who spend excessive time on the internet (addiction), betting in the internet, and use of mobile hand set in class during lectures, watching of pornographic pictures and videos, missing class, test and failure to submit assignments. According to Scott (2004), students that extremely use the internet may possess uncontrollable behaviour that is impossible to stop or interest towards the internet which may result to unhealthy life style and severely upset feelings.

More so, the internet provides students with continuous access to family members, friends and other social groups to get social support. Thus, access and usage of the internet may bring about increase stress and tension. Through various internet tools such as the e-mail, social network like Whatsapp, facebook, 2go, badoo, imo, twitter, Instagram, and so forth, students are able to communicate, interact and connect with family members, relations and friends. Anderson (2009) reported that students who use the internet extremely too much may encounter a drop in their study habit, exhaustion, loneliness and sleeplessness. Some students feel that life without the internet is boring therefore they show clear preference to internet as a medium for interaction and leisure activities. Sometimes students often look unstable, restless, exhausted and depressed when they make effort to reduce the time they spend on the internet. Also, they are always looking forward and eyeing the next interaction online. Sometimes students lie to their parents and lecturers to conceal the amount of time spent on the internet which they see as a way of escaping from problem of unstable behaviour such as having a feeling of guilt and stress. Davis (2008) opined that the act of spending extreme time on the internet results to disregard of school responsibilities and keeping away from classes which result to unsatisfactory academic performance.

Studies done on problems of Internet access and usage include effects of personal relationship and communication in internet room (Bellamy & Hanewisz (2001). Brown & Duguid (1996) investigated the influence of internet on academic performance of students. The finding of the study showed that students' academic performance was influenced negatively by the internet. Beida (2008) examined internet use, abuse or dependence among Students of University of Maiduguri. The findings of the study showed that those who spend excessive time on line encounter a drop in their academic performances. Paul, Baker & Cochran (2012) in their study surveyed effect of online social networking on student academic performance. The study revealed that too much

internet usage affects in a negative way students' performance. Whyte (2008) asserted that focusing on one's study and moderately using the internet no doubt will bring about a higher academic performance. It is against this backdrop that this study explored Internet access and usage: its impact on students' academic performance in secondary Social Studies.

2. Statement of the Problem

The internet is a networking system through the computer and (ICT) which is controlled from a centralised monitor, where information is being diffused and passed to everybody globally. There are a lot of gains students and the generality of the society derive from the use of the internet. It is very significant to students because it has the possibility to make faster and more efficient and to reduce administrative challenges or task and make achievable greater effectiveness and productivity in the management of the educational system. Students are able to retrieve information and data through the availability of the internet. Ojedokun (2009) affirms that with recent development in information technology, no serious student will depend solely on his/her lecturers; they need the internet to support and authenticate facts and knowledge learnt or acquired in the classroom.

However, despite the numerous advantages and benefit of the internet to the educational and social environments, it's access and usage excessive usage by students is not without its disadvantages which includes internet abuse, and compulsiveness, internet addiction, abandoning academic activities, going late to lectures, abstinence from classes, not submitting assignment, gambling and viewing of pornographic pictures and videos. Internet access and usage has been associated with missing classes, course failure and dismissal from school. It is with regards to the aforementioned that this study addressed Internet access and usage: its impact on students' academic performance in secondary Social Studies.

2.1 Hypotheses

Ho₁ There is no significance relationship between internet access and usage for academic motive and students' academic performance.

Ho₂ There is no significance relationship between Internet access and usage on students assignment submission.

Ho₃ There is no significance relationship between time spent on the internet and students' academic performance.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

This study is built on Bloom's (1968) theory of Learning for Mastery. According to Bloom (1968) student ability to learn a given subject or course of study is tied to a guide of the time students spent would need to learn the subject to a given level, not an index of the level or stage to which a student could learn the subject in a given amount of time. He went further to state strongly that that if each student was allowed the time he

needed to learn the subject to some judgement requirement or criterion level, and if he spent the required time to do this, then he would probably reach that level (high academic performance). But students who did not spend the needed or demanded, the extent to which such students would learn could be stated as:

$$\text{Degree of school learning} = f \left(\frac{\text{Time spent}}{\text{Time needed}} \right)$$

So, the degree of school learning which in this case is student academic performance would be a function of the time the student actually spent in learning.

It also shows that time spent, assignment submission and students test attendance play an imperative role in students' academic performance. The relevance of this theory to this study lies on the fact that perseverance, opportunity to learn, or the time needed to learn is determined time spent. Bloom opined that student's perseverance is as the degree of time the student is willing to spend aggressively and actively for academic purposes. If student spent their time positively along with the teaching activities, their academic performance or output will improve or reach a higher level. And as regard these outputs, the distinction between the students will be at the minimum level. The main thrust of the theory is that the amount or extent of time spent on study has a substantial impact on student academic performance.

3. Literature Review

3.1 Internet Access and Usage and Students' Academic Performance

Geri & Grace-Martin (2001) noted that the fact that there are now results which showed significant relationship between internet usage and students' academic performance, hints that measurable features of looking at website for too long can be useful predictors of meaning behavioural outputs variables that may include number of browsing sessions and duration of surfing the internet correlated with students' final grades. However, utilisation of the internet did predict GPA obtained after a year of access. This effect of internet usage on students' academic performance was unbroken throughout the study. The findings of several studies have revealed significant relationship between internet usage and students' academic performance. Geri & Grace-Martin (2001) stated that the product of the finding in their study was as a result of the text heavy nature of internet. Students' access to the volume of information and interaction provided by the internet, help students complete their homework and other studies. Also the internet tools associated with spending time with and talking with people through the internet help students to study with their peers.

Griffiths (1996) observed that the quantity of time exhausted or spent on the internet is not as important as quality of time spent on the internet when talking about students' internet usage and performance. Specifically, when the quality of the usage of the internet, especially when excessive, is not closely guided, and confirmed that more harm than good could be done to student academic achievement when students spend

lots of time using the internet. Some studies have showed positive impact of excessive use of the internet and academic achievement of students. An investigation by Kolek & Saunders (2008) in their study on internet usage and students' academic performance, the result of the study showed that there was no significant relationship between too much usage of the internet and academic performance. In almost the same way, an exploratory survey study showed excessive internet usage affects students' academic performance negatively. In another dimension, Karpinski & Duberstein (2009) in their study on the relationship between heavy internet use and students' academic performance showed a negative significant relationship.

However, Davis (2008) as well as Paul, Bakeer & Cochran (2012) observed that students who spent so much time on the internet for non-academic motive have always shown to prefer spending too much time surfing the net which act as distractions or actions that interfere with mental focus to them because of the time devoted to it.

3.2 Motivations for Using the Internet

Kubey, Lavin & Barrows (2001) asserted that internet user make use of the internet to connect with others, bring to mind the importance of studying the motives or purposes for using the internet. Lam, Peng, Mai & Ing, (2009) reported that the individuals or people who spend excessive time on the internet, do so to gain a sense of control in their lives and to reinforce self-esteem, also demonstrations the significance of looking at the role of motives when investigating predictors of excessive internet usage. Kaye & Johnson (2004) precisely stated that people use the internet for a different kind of interpersonal such as for affection, inclusion, social interaction, and so on, and media related motives like passing time, entertainment/pleasure, information seeking, leisure, escape, and so on.

LaRose, Lin, & Eastin (2003) opined that some researches have looked into the effect of motives for using the internet on both internet reliance and internet addiction. However, there are few researches that have really investigated the possible connection between ranges of motives individual have for being addicted to the internet. Specifically, it has been contended that more purpose and instrumental use of the internet (e.g. information seeking, control, caring, others, etc.) may hinder or block negative results. According to Song, LaRose, Eastin, & Lin (2004), the more habitual use (e.g., habitual entertainment, escape) encourages the probability of unintentional and possibly negative outcomes of use.

3.3 Benefits of Internet Usage for Academics

Rainie & Packel (2001) reported that students are generally positive about the internet and its impacts on their educational experience. The study also discovered that majority of higher institution students have positive attitude toward the internet. They find the internet useful and are comfortable with its communication, along with even give account of its enjoyment while using it for academic and personal reasons. Their purpose of using the internet is divided between academic and social uses, and they find it functional for both purpose. A great number of students are of the belief that

internet have positively improve or enhance their college academic knowledge or experience. The internet is employed or utilised in most cases to augment students' scholarship activities and provide some options for teachers and students looking to bring new life to well-known educational experiences.

Fatoki (2004) asserted that internet usage in Nigeria started in 1995, and ever since a lot of organizations and institutions of learning have been connected to enhance their corporate output and objectives. Jagboro (2003) stated that students make use of the internet usage for research purposes. Lubans (1999) opined that the internet positively influences students' academic work and performance. Students have access to enough facts and information like internet reference materials and sources. The internet makes available enriched information on day-to-day events and the newest views since it is easier to access, its' fun, interesting and it exposes students to a large quantity of materials and inspire the students to do more reading or study.

3.4 Internet Usage and Students Assignment Submission

With the easy access to the internet for immeasurable number of students on, the internet is used by students surfing social network websites as well as for a wide range of purposes that can be largely classified into education and non-education purposes (Jacobsen & Forste, 2011). According to Kubey, Lavin & Barrows (2001), internet used for educational purposes include students using the internet to enhance their knowledge related to their academic interests (for example, online assignment manager, watching news and videos relevant to the student's academic courses, and so forth).

The internet used for non-educational motive or purposes are more often than not related to entertainment. Example of internet for non-academic motives include online movie watching, listening to music online, online gaming, watching television using the internet, and so forth. Anand (2007) and Fox, Rosen, & Crawford (2009) opined that previous and present studies have returned negative correlation between spending much time on the internet and students' academic success or achievement. According to Jacobsen & Forste (2011), due to the fact that most studies concentrated on the investigation of time spent on the internet; not much research has been done specifically to deal with the issue of excessive internet usage and assignment submission.

3.5 Effect of Time Spent on the Internet on Students Academic Performance

Technology has changed speedily over time. Where people used to spend an extended amount of time watching television, currently there has been a shift into spending more time on the internet, where a wider range of activities are accessible. This can be seen by the recent popularity and the several options of activities that can be done using the internet. In a study by Misra, Patterson, Lundmark, Kiesler, & Scherlis (1995) to evaluate the effects of time spent on the internet and students' academic performance, the finding of the study disclosed that there is no significant effect of time spent online and students' academic performance. However, with the internet, there has been noticeable social influence for individuals to use the internet to be up dated with

information from the outside world. According to Chen & Peng (2008), some may argue that internet utilization is of many benefits though there has been a large amount of researches that has connected excessive internet usage and poor academic performance.

Various researchers have concluded that a percentage of internet users perceived that online use have negative bearing on their lives. Majority of the problems connected to internet use are issues of development, pornography, daily activities reduction, depression and sleep problems, academic/school dismissal and dropout, social isolation, online gambling, stalking, and binge drinking among students. The major issues that students are mostly concern with is developmental and academic dismissal issues (Anderson, 2009). Chen & Peng (2010) found that students spend 17 hours weekly on websites making friends & chatting, searching for non-academic and academic information, playing games, and read-through emails. Exact websites that they discovered visited the most were social media, and searching for scholastic materials to boost their performance. The study observed that those who spend lesser time on the internet had better academic performance than those who spend much time on the internet users. The purpose or motive of using the internet includes recreational and academic purposes. Most times students are spending or devoting their treasurable time on the internet at the detriment of school work, which undeniably could have a resilient effect on their academic performance. A student confirmed that Facebook social media definitely interferes with his academic activities (Pychi, 2008).

According to Mutz, Roberts & van Vuuren (1993) adolescents have a limited amount of time. Therefore, expending huge time in non-educational usage of the Internet may hinder their academic performance. When students increase the time spent on the internet involving in social and/leisure or recreational activities, time expended or sacrifices will have to be created in other aspects, like time spent on completion of assignments, reading, and studying (Neuman, 1991). This displacement and unsatisfactory performance may occur for the internet, which entertains or interest adolescents with exciting images besides audio-visual effects, is more appealing than school study. Consequently, using the time spent on the internet may result to the displacement or lack of interest of academic activities, as did television, and will eventually impede or decrease students' performance (Shin, 2004; Shejwal & Purayidathil, 2006). The use of the Internet has become very popular among tertiary institution students. Indeed, with the coming of the internet students were among the first group to make use of the internet on a large scale, and also the first to come across problems connected with excessive Internet usage (Beida, 2008). According to Jones (2002), the present generation of students grew up at a time they can be introduced to the internet into at very tender age. The fact that students could carried away by the internet without much control has resulted to considerable debate, controversy and ongoing research. However, existing literature has clearly indicated that users are experiencing negative consequences from the time they spent on the internet (Anderson, 2001).

3.6 Empirical on Internet usage and Students' Academic Performance

In line with the study of Cox (2000) who examined the effect of the social networking, attitudes and habits among college students in Britain. A population of 433 college students were given questionnaires, while a simple random technique was used. The result of the finding shows that college students are frequently uses of social media. Adding that the age subsets, is between 15-24years. Ojedokun (2001) investigated the relationship between problem of internet usage and academic performance of students in Boston, 706 undergraduate students were administered with questionnaires. A simple random sampling technique was used for 301 male and 405 female students. The result indicates that a large percentage or ratio of students recounted feelings of detachment and symptoms or signs of in tolerance, withdrawal and escape.

Scherer (2007) investigated problematic internet usage among students in Boston. A total Number of 706 respondents were administered with questionnaire. A simple sample technique employed for (301 males and 405 females). It was found out that a large proportion of students reported feeling of dissociation and indicates symptoms of low tolerance, withdrawal and escape. Also, it affects their academic performance. Whyte (2008) examined correlation between excessive internet usage and academic success of students. Result from the study revealed that there was negative correlation between excessive internet usage and performance of students. A study conducted by Anderson (2009) revealed that college students who use the internet excessively experience a deterioration in study habit, loss of sleep and loneliness.

Ojedokun (2009) Examined online habits and attitudes of undergraduates at midsize university in the middle East, and found that large majority of students (80%) used one or more social networking sites (facebook, Whatsapp, Imo, Instagram, and so on). A population of 1,530 was sampled (753 males and 774 females). A simple random sampling technique was used the result of was that students who use the internet most heavily may perform below expectation academically. A study by Chen & Tzeng (2010) also looked at what exactly college students were spending their time doing online, as well as looking at the differences between genders. Their study revealed that female heavy users did well in their performance when they favoured information searching and chatting, nevertheless felt more depressed and unhappy compared to non-heavy users; female heavy users had lower academic performance when they favoured information seeking, chatting, and online gaming, and had greater loneliness, physical illness, and depression than non-heavy users; male heavy users had lower academic performance when they favoured online games; male heavy users were more likely to feel physically ill, unhappy and depressed if they favoured chatting, looking for information, and online games. Kirschner & Karpinski (2010) investigated the impact of over-involvement with social networking on students' academic performance. The result of the study showed that students over-involvement with social networking have negative impacts on their academic performance.

Chen, Lambert & Guidry (2010) carried out a study on the amount of time students spent online in Canadian University. The study focused on youth in grades 6th-10th found that 41 % of females and 34% of males watched two hours or less of

television per day. This contrasts significantly when they appraised the amount of time spent online. In this context 18% of females and 14% of males were on the net for two hours or less per day. Reynol, Merson & Salter (2010) investigated if there is significant relationship between multiple indices of Facebook usage and students' academic performance. The finding of the study showed that there is negative significant relationship between multiple indices of Facebook usage and students' academic performance. Ahmed & Qazi (2011) investigated students' perception of satisfaction for maintenance on class performance. The result indicated that 76.5% of the students sampled agreed that they could maintain their class achievement, while only 10.3% stated otherwise. In his study, Cull (2011) investigated the impact of internet on variety of disciplines on the technological, social, behavioural and neuron-scientific on students' self-study. A precise emphasis was allocated to the reading behaviour of emergent university students. The study revealed negative effects on students' self-study.

Ogedebe (2012) explore the extent of usage of internet among Nigerian University, undergraduate and who it has affected the academic performance in a university at Maduguri, a questionnaire was administered to a total number of 350 respondents who completed and returned the questionnaire. The result of this founding was that the internet services are fully exploited by the students and this has affected their academic performances either negatively or positively. Paul, Baker and Cochran (2012) investigated the impact of social networks on students' academic performance. The finding of this study indicated that there is a significant impact of social network usage on students' academic performance. Rosen, Carrier, & Cheever (2013) in their study on the effects of Facebook social media on students' self-study. The result of the study revealed that students cope with their self-study and also interact or correspond with the virtual environment effectively.

4. Methodology

4.1 Research Design

The design for this study was correlational research design. It involves the investigation of the extent to which the variation in one factor or variable corresponds with the variation in one or more factor or variable based on correlation co-efficient.

4.2 Population of the Study

The population consisted of 55,303 male and female upper basic education students from one hundred and sixty-one public secondary schools. Most of the respondents were female (65%) and male (35%) aged between 12 to 14 years old. Female students dominated the sample, which is consistent with the current gender ratio among secondary school students in Nigeria.

4.3 Sample and Sampling Techniques

The sample of the study comprised 576 students selected through stratified sampling technique from UBE schools. To determine the sample size, balloting with replacement technique was used to draw out forty-seven (48) students from the population of each of the twelve schools selected for the study used for the study.

4.4 Instruments of the Study

The following instruments were used in the study:

1. Students' academic performance records (results): the records of students' academic performance were collected and used through the help of the class teachers and principals in their respective schools.
2. Questionnaire: The questionnaire was designed to measure internet access and usage and students' academic performance. The questionnaire contained two sections, section A' and B' section 'A' contain personal information of the respondents, while section "B" had 24 items instrument. The 24-items in the questionnaire were put into clusters as follows cluster A internet access and usage for academic motive (8), cluster B-assignment submission (8), cluster C-excessive time spent (8). The items in these sections were rated on 4 points scale as follows. SA (strongly Agree) 4, A (Agree) 2 D (Disagree) 3, and S.D. (Strongly Disagree) 1

4.5 Data Analysis

The data to be collected were arrayed and grouped according to the factors presented in tables and analysed statistically using correlational statistics at 0.05 level of significant.

5. Results

Hypothesis 1

There is no significance relationship between internet access and usage for academic motive and students' academic performance.

Table 1: Correlation for internet access and usage for academic motive and students' academic performance

		Internet Usage	Academic Performance
Internet Access and Usage	Pearson Correlation	1	.530**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	576	576
Academic Performance	Pearson Correlation	.530**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	576	576

Table 1 shows the testing of relationship between internet access and usage for academic motive and students' academic performance for significance; the result shows

that there was significant relationship between internet access and usage for academic motive and students' academic performance. In the correlation matrix table, the Person Product moment correlation coefficient analysis indicates that the variables of the observed relationships were fairly strong (0.530) were strength of correlation is between +0.9 and +0.5 or -0.9 and -0.5 else weak. The relationship coefficient between students' internet access and usage for academic motive and their academic performance is ($r=.530$) and thus shows positive correlation. There is a significant relationship between internet access and usage for academic motive and their academic performance. The correlation matrix shows a significance of 0.000 at $P<0.05$ level of significance (2-tailed). The decision rule is that since the correlations coefficient ($r=0.530$) and level of significance (0.000) is less than $P<0.05$ level of significance therefore the null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, there is significant relationship between internet access and usage for academic work and students' academic performance.

The students seem generally positive about the Internet and its impact on their academic performance and educational experience. The majority of the students (78%) have a positive attitude concerning the internet, its tools and usage. They are at ease with internet access and usage, and even report having satisfaction and excitement while using it for personal and academic motives/purposes.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significance relationship between internet access and usage and assignment submission.

Table 2: Correlation for internet access and usage and students Assignment Submission

		Internet Usage	Assignment Submission
Internet Access and Usage	Pearson Correlation	1	.105*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.012
	N	576	576
Assignment Submission	Pearson Correlation	.105*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.012	
	N	576	576

Table 2 shows the testing of relationship between internet access and usage and students assignment submission rate for significance; the result shows that there is significant relationship between internet access and usage and students assignment submission. In the correlation matrix table, the Person Product moment correlation coefficient analysis indicates that the variables of the observed relationships were weak (0.105). The relationship coefficient between students' internet access and usage and their assignment submission is ($r=.105$) and thus shows positive correlation. There is significant relationship between students' internet usage and their assignment submission rate. The correlation matrix shows a significance of 0.012 at $P<0.05$ level of significance (2-tailed). The decision rule is that since the correlations coefficient ($r=0.105$) and level of significance (0.012) is less than $P<0.05$ level of significance therefore the null

hypothesis is rejected. Thus, there is significant relationship between internet access and usage on students' assignment submission.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significance relationship between time spent on the internet and students' academic performance.

Table 3: Correlation for Time Spent on the internet and students' Academic Performance

		Internet Usage	Academic Performance
Internet Usage	Pearson Correlation	1	.530**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	576	576
Academic Performance	Pearson Correlation	.530**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	576	576

Table 3 shows the testing of relationship between time spent on the internet and students' academic performance for significance; the result shows that there was significant relationship between time spent on the internet and students' academic performance. In the correlation matrix table, the Person Product moment correlation coefficient analysis indicates that the variables of the observed relationships were fairly strong (0.530) were strength of correlation is between +0.9 and +0.5 or -0.9 and -0.5 else weak. The relationship coefficient between students' internet usage and their academic performance is ($r=.530$) and thus shows positive correlation. There is a significant relationship between time spent on the internet and students' academic performance. The correlation matrix shows a significance of 0.000 at $P<0.05$ level of significance (2-tailed). The decision rule is that since the correlations coefficient ($r=0.530$) and level of significance (0.000) is less than $P<0.05$ level of significance therefore the null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, there is significant relationship between time spent on the internet for academic work and students' academic performance.

We found it fascinating that there was a between the subjects' academic performance and time spent on the internet. This implies that, in reality, students with a higher academic performance spend a lesser amount of time on the internet, but this is not reflected in their views. Thus, the aforementioned facts make us to believe that the choice of how much time to spend online is not made at a conscious level.

6. Discussion of Results

6.1 Internet Access and Usage and Students' Academic Performance

The result of the study disclosed that there is significant relationship between internet access and usage and students' academic performance and that the observed relationships was strong, thus shows positive correlation. The finding that there was positive relationship between internet access and usage for academic motive and students' academic performance did not come as a surprise since research has

demonstrated that internet access and usage for academic work no doubt improve academic performance. Moreover, observing a correlation between internet access and usage for academic work and performance is not out of place. More time using the internet was linked with better reading comprehension and academic performance. This finding is in agreement with the works of Lubans (1999), Geri & Grace-Martin (2001) and Zha & Lei (2006) and who had earlier reported that there is significant positive relationship between internet access and usage for academic motive and students' academic performance but in disagreement with Carvin (2006), Kolek & Saunders (2008), Reynol, Merson & Salter (2010) who reported no significant positive relationship between internet access and usage for academic motive and students' academic performance.

Rainie & Packel (2001) observed that noted that the positive significant relationship between internet access and usage for academic work and students' academic performance is understandable. According to them, an awesome number of students are of the view that internet usage has positively and greatly improved and enriched their academic experience. And that majority of students are of positive view and attitude as regard the internet and its interaction tools. They are contented and satisfied with internet interaction/communication, and equally testify finding satisfaction while utilising it for scholastic/educational and personal reasons. In many cases, the internet is utilised to supplement or augment students' educational activities and offer some options for instructors/teachers and students exploring to bring innovation to familiar educational experiences.

The accessibility of the internet is likely alluring students to depend very heavily on it when searching for academic materials and resources. This participant went on to describe that the internet, rather than the library, is the principal source of their information searches. Majority of students said they use less of the library compared to the internet. Findings from data indicated that negative impact of internet access and usage would occur due to their extensive Internet usage. Furthermore, the study supports the arguments that the internet can play a negative impact on academic performance if used mainly for recreational activities. Ogedebe (2012) have also found proofs indicating that accessing and utilising the internet, chiefly for academic work, contributes significantly to higher academic performance. This could be connected with the reality that users have discovered great reservoir and source of information in diverse disciplines amidst scarcity of books in libraries. So, it is based on this that bulk of the students use the internet for academic purposes, it could be acknowledged that the internet empowers students to solve and explain their academic problems. This position conveys the fact that there is significant relationship between students' internet usage and their performance. Therefore, depending on the way of thinking and maturity of the Internet user, one can prioritize their focus on proper use of it. So the study finding is that, by appropriate focusing and internet information world usage, better result can be attained. Generally, the study result collaborates with that in which the respondents professed that the internet as a complement for learning hence improving their academic performance.

6.2 Internet Usage and Assignment Submission

Results of data analysis also revealed that there is significant relationship between internet access and usage and students' assignment submission. This means that internet access and usage has no effect on students' assignment submission. The implication of this finding is that with the easy access to the Internet for a vast majority of students, the Internet is not only used by students for visiting social network websites, but for education purpose, thus, influencing students' assignment submission. This finding concurs with those of Kubey, Lavin & Barrows (2001); Jacobsen & Forste (2011) who reported significant relationship between internet access and usage and students' assignment submission. This is expected, because recent and past studies have shown positive relationship and association between students' assignment submission and internet access and usage of the internet (includes offline and online media usage). Students internet used for academic purposes help to improve their knowledge pertinent to their academic interests and to find solution to assignment task, therefore result in prompt assignment submission.

These findings submit that the internet aid students' academic work and learning experiences, characterized by internet access and usage, can potentially affect positively students' assignment submission. For these participants, the internet instead appeared to be an effective tool for academic work such as assignment submission, a universal digital library and fastest way to get or grasp knowledge. This collaborate Asdaque, Khan & Rizvi (2010) who reported that students who used internet for downloading assignment and books/journal have higher rate of assignment completion and submission and better academic performance as compared to those who used internet for other than assignment or downloading software/songs. Also with Ahmed & Qazi (2011) who argue that students manage their time efficiently and fulfill their academic or school work and assignment requirements effectively, hence internet usage have no adverse impact on their academic work and academic performance. Specifically, students utilise the internet to search for information for academic work, communication with people regarding schoolwork and other school assignments, and to enhance their learning and understanding. It is a pertinent source of information which facilitates academic research. Our findings also appear to diverge from prior research that has suggested that internet usage have negative impact on students' academic and assignment submission (e.g., Kolek, 2008). The internet makes available enriched information on events daily and the newest views since it is easier to access, it's fun, interesting and it exposes students to a large quantity of materials and inspire the students to do more reading or study.

6.3 Time Spent on the Internet and Students' Academic Performance

Regarding time spent on the internet and students' academic performance, the present study revealed there was there was significant relationship between time spent on the internet and students' academic performance. In other words, the results show that there was there was significant relationship between time spent on the internet and students' academic performance which confirmed with conclusions found by previous

studies. The main reason for this is that increased amounts of time in educational use of the Internet may enhance students' academic performance. This finding is in agreement with Misra, Patterson, Lundmark, Kiesler, & Scherlis (1995), and [Keith & Barry \(1999\)](#) in their study on time spent on the internet and students' academic performance found significant relationship between time spent on the internet and students' academic performance. This is in conformity with the present study. While quite opposite results are found that there is no significant relationship between time spent on the internet and students' academic performance by Mutz, Roberts & van Vuuren (1993), Shejwal & Purayidathil (2006), Scherer (2007), Whyte (2008), Kirschner & Karpinski (2010) and Chen & Peng (2010) where time spent on the internet result in the supplanting of academic activities and eventually decrease students' academic performance.

Enjoying access to volume of information that the internet offers help students to accomplish homework and socializing devices or tools support and help students' schoolwork with their classmates and peers. Hence, the strong correlation between time spent on the internet and academic performance. Therefore, increased extent of time on academic and scholastic use of the internet will not hinder students' academic performance rather improve their performance. When students increase the time spent on the internet engross in social as well as/or recreational and frivolous activities, time sacrifices in other areas, such as studying, reading, and doing assignments will have to be made. The finding of this study accentuates the multifaceted characteristics of the structure of internet usage. The common postulation is that more time used or spent on the internet implies that students are getting addicted to it but our data does not support this relationship. Our data also submits that time spent on the internet does not imply academic failure. The task to regulate the time spent on the internet does not appear predominantly valuable in enhancing the probabilities of academic success. Most significantly, the results point out that increased amounts of time in educational use of the Internet may enhance students' academic performance.

7. Conclusion of the Study

The study has provided empirical basis on the impact of excessive internet usage for academic motive and students' academic performance. This is seen in the fact that there is a relationship between internet access and usage for academic motive and students' academic performance. The study has also revealed a relationship between internet access and usage and students' assignment submission. Furthermore, the impact of internet access and usage cannot be determined immediately. It can only be assumed that based on the result and observations made, there is a relationship between internet access and usage and students' academic performance.

7.1 Recommendations

1. Students should utilise the internet to improve their academic performance by restricting or limiting themselves to academic purposes since non-academic motives might have adverse impact in their academic achievement.

2. Teachers should evolve regulations to guide the extent of Internet usage to avert getting to the point of over dependency among student population.
3. Students need to be counselled on the danger of excessive usage of the Internet.
4. Students should be properly educated on how to make fruitful use of the internet.
5. Counselling centres or students' representative body should organise seminars to create awareness among faculty, staff, administrators, and students on the consequences of excessive Internet usage on campus.

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